

DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES AND ITS PROSPECTS

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Annotasiya. Ushbu maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida ta'lim xizmatlarining rivojlanish zarurligi bayon qilinib unga ko'ra talim sohasini raqamlashtirish O'zbekiston kelajak avlodini shakllantirishda yangi davrni boshlab berishi alohida fikr va yondashuvlar asosida ifoda etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'lim xizmatlari, o'quv dasturlari, big data, machine learning, texnologik innovatsiyalar, onlayn o'qitish, e-larning, learning analytics, artificial intelligence.

Abstract: In this article, the need for the development of educational services in the digital economy is described, and according to it, the digitization of the education sector will start a new era in the formation of the future generation of Uzbekistan based on different ideas and approaches.

Keywords: Educational services, educational programs, big data, machine learning, technological innovations, online education, e-learning, learning analytics, artificial intelligence.

Аннотация: В данной статье описывается необходимость развития образовательных услуг в условиях цифровой экономики, и согласно ей цифровизация сферы образования положит начало новой эре в формировании будущего поколения Узбекистана на основе разных идей и подходов.

Ключевые слова: Образовательные услуги, образовательные программы, большие данные, машинное обучение, технологические инновации, онлайнобразование, электронное обучение, учебная аналитика, искусственный интеллект.

The development of the digital economy today affects all areas of the economy. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. In the 46th goal of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" approved by Mirziyoyev, special attention was paid to the development of educational services. In particular, in the Republic, the task of "raising the level of coverage with higher education to 50% and "increasing the quality of education in the development of the service sector and the use of digital and innovative technologies in the reduction of poverty" [1] has been set. Also, "granting academic and financial independence to state higher education institutions, including establishing the practice of

independent determination of wages, the number of employees, the amount of payment contracts and the form of education by them" 31 is considered one of the important tasks. The field of education, as one of the areas defining the economy of the future, requires the introduction of the digital economy and the use of new digital technologies on this basis. In particular, the systematic introduction of the digital economy in the education sector of our republic creates the opportunity to provide quality education based on "artificial intelligence" based on the following processes, as well as automation of the field, quality organization of the education system using modern mathematical models and special methods, and the use of computer programs. In our republic, the introduction of the digital economy into the field of education serves as an important factor in solving several problems in higher, secondary, and secondary special education [2].

In our opinion, the potential of local higher education institutions is not sufficiently put into practice. The consequences of this are manifested not only in the low inflow of extra-budgetary funds to higher education institutions due to the implementation of research and development, but also directly in the decrease in the qualification level of professors. To provide scientific research developments or consulting services, professors and teachers are required to constantly improve their potential. This encourages professors and teachers to do more research in solving current scientific, technical, and other problems [3]. Based on the above, we believe that it is necessary to create educational, information-analytical centers in higher education institutions as shown in the table (Table 1).

Table 1

The main tasks of educational, information-analytical centers of higher educational institutions.

Type of activity Duties	Types of consulting services
Educational activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - directing enterprises and attracting venture investors; - providing enterprises with expert assistance in contacting venture investors, including venture fairs; - consulting support to innovative enterprises in the region;
Education and training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - development of practical skills for interaction with potential investors, in this case, most importantly, development of skills of managers of enterprises to effectively present their business projects to successfully attract venture investments; - development of practical skills for interaction with potential investors, in this case, most importantly, development of skills of managers of enterprises to effectively present their business projects to successfully attract venture investments;
Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - conducting various communication events (venture fairs in the regions, roundtables, thematic conferences, seminars, etc.) and providing consulting and information services to the main subjects of innovative activity;

Creating a high image of a higher education institution has a practical purpose, which is to attract more applicants, and establish relations with companies, public organizations, and various funds, as a result, to ensure an increase in the flow of financial resources to the higher education institution. It should be noted that in world practice, great attention is paid to increasing the efficiency of the educational system. In some cases, there is a tendency to increase the duration of education, which means reducing the duration of a person's productive activity. All this means

that higher education must adequately respond to these new challenges and effectively solve new problems. At the same time, attention should be paid to the creation and application of new methods and forms of education, as well as to the formation of innovative, creative thinking among students [4].

In conclusion, the high potential of higher educational institutions allows them to make a significant contribution to the innovative development of an important fund-creating field such as construction. A system should be created that ensures the transfer of knowledge and technologies from the environment of OTM to production to regularly use the knowledge obtained as a result of the scientific and intellectual activities of OTM for commercial purposes. Such a system can be focused on attracting private investments to encourage higher education institutions to create innovative inventions, increase the number of patents issued for these inventions, and support scientific and intellectual activities in the field of higher education.

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